

Comparative Radiological Outcomes of Stand-Alone PEEK Cage Versus PEEK Cage with Anterior Plating in Single-Level ACDF: A Prospective Study

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Abstract

Objective: To evaluate and compare the radiological findings of cage subsidence and segmental kyphosis after single-level ACDF performed with stand-alone PEEK cages versus PEEK cages with anterior plating.

Material and Methods: This quasi-experimental study was conducted at the Department of Neurosurgery Unit-III, Punjab Institute of Neurosciences, Lahore General Hospital, Lahore. Forty patients with single-level cervical degenerative disc disease (aged 30–60 years) were included using convenient sampling and randomized into two groups of 20 patients each via balloting. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm SD, and qualitative variables as frequencies and percentages. Independent t-test and chi-square test were applied, with significance at $p < 0.05$. Data was entered and analyzed by the computer program SPSS version 26.

Results: Both groups were comparable in baseline demographics. In Group A (stand-alone PEEK cage), 65% were female with mean age 44.70 ± 8.151 years. In Group B (with plating), 60% were female with mean age 42.40 ± 9.196 years ($p = 0.850$). The most common operative level was C5-6 in both groups.

Conclusion: ACDF using PEEK cage with anterior plating demonstrated superior radiological outcomes with significantly lower rates of cage subsidence and segmental kyphosis compared to stand-alone PEEK cage at 6-month follow-up. Anterior plating provides better mechanical stability and maintenance of segmental alignment in single-level procedures.

Keywords: Anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF), PEEK cage, anterior plating, cage subsidence, segmental kyphosis, cervical degenerative disc disease.

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Introduction

The cervical spine, consisting of seven vertebrae, is highly susceptible to degenerative changes with advancing age. Anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) remain the gold standard surgical intervention for symptomatic single-level cervical disc disease unresponsive to conservative management.¹

First popularized by Smith-Robinson and Cloward in the late 1950s, the procedure has evolved with the introduction of interbody cages, particularly polyetheretherketone (PEEK) cages, which offer radiolucency, biomechanical compatibility, and reduced donor-site morbidity compared to autograft.²

Despite these advancements, challenges persist, including cage subsidence (settling of the cage into the adjacent vertebral endplates) and loss of segmental lordosis leading to kyphotic deformity.³ These complications can compromise foraminal height, contribute to adjacent segment degeneration, and affect long-term clinical outcomes. Anterior plating has been proposed as an adjunct to enhance initial stability, prevent graft/cage migration, and maintain sagittal alignment.⁴

Extensive literature supports the use of PEEK cages in ACDF due to their elastic modulus close to bone, promoting better load sharing and fusion visualization.

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However, stand-alone cages have been associated with higher subsidence rates (ranging from 15–50% in various studies) and increased risk of segmental kyphosis, particularly when endplates are violated or in multi-level constructs.⁵

Others consistently demonstrate that supplemental anterior plating reduces subsidence and maintains better segmental lordosis, although clinical outcomes may not always differ significantly in short-term follow-up for single-level disease.⁶ Plating adds stability by counteracting the compressive forces during the early fusion phase but carries risks such as dysphagia, adjacent level ossification, and increased operative time.⁷

The current study adds to this body of evidence by providing prospective quasi-experimental data from a Pakistani tertiary care setting.⁸

This study specifically investigated the comparative radiological efficacy of stand-alone PEEK cages versus PEEK cages augmented with anterior plating in single-level ACDF, focusing on subsidence and segmental kyphosis.

Material and Methods

This study was designed as a quasi-experimental study conducted at the Department of Neurosurgery Unit-III, Punjab Institute of Neurosciences (PINS), Lahore General Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. The study duration was twelve months following approval of the research synopsis by the institutional review board. Approval from the Ethical Committee of the University of Health Sciences / Lahore General Hospital was obtained prior to commencement of the study. All patients provided written informed consent after a detailed explanation of the procedure, risks, benefits, and alternative options.

A total of 40 patients with single-level symptomatic cervical degenerative disc disease were enrolled using a convenient sampling technique. The sample size of 40 was calculated using the standard formula for finite population correction, aiming for a 95% confidence level with a 5% margin of error. Patients were divided into two equal groups of 20 patients each through balloting (simple randomization by lottery method). Group A underwent Anterior Cervical Discectomy and Fusion (ACDF) using a stand-alone PEEK (Polyetheretherketone) cage, while Group B underwent ACDF using a PEEK cage supplemented with anterior cervical plating.

Inclusion Criteria were patients aged between 30 and 60 years with clinical and radiological evidence of single-level cervical degenerative disc disease (confirmed on MRI and CT) causing radiculopathy or myelopathy refractory to conservative management. Exclusion Criteria included patients with previous cervical spine surgery, metabolic bone disease (e.g., osteoporosis, osteomalacia), active systemic or local infection, trauma, tumor, multilevel

disease, or involvement of the C7-T1 level (where adequate radiological visualization is often suboptimal).

All surgeries were performed by the same surgical team using the standard Smith-Robinson anterior cervical approach under general anesthesia with endotracheal intubation. A transverse right-sided skin incision of 1–2 inches was made along a natural skin crease. The dissection was carried out in the standard fashion between the carotid sheath laterally and the trachea/esophagus medially to reach the prevertebral fascia. The correct disc level was confirmed intraoperatively using fluoroscopy. Microscopic anterior cervical discectomy was performed, including complete removal of the diseased disc material, decompression of the neural elements, removal of osteophytes, and gentle resection of the cartilaginous endplates to expose bleeding subchondral bone. The posterior longitudinal ligament was opened when necessary to ensure adequate decompression.

In both groups, a appropriately sized PEEK cage filled with autologous cancellous bone (harvested locally or from minimal iliac crest if required) was inserted into the prepared disc space under gentle distraction to restore disc height and segmental alignment. In Group A, the procedure was completed with the stand-alone PEEK cage without additional instrumentation. In Group B, supplemental fixation was achieved using an anterior cervical titanium locking plate with variable-angle screws placed into the adjacent vertebral bodies. Hemostasis was secured, and a drain was placed in selected cases. Postoperative immobilization consisted of a hard Philadelphia cervical collar for 6 weeks followed by a soft cervical collar for an additional 2 weeks in both groups.

Radiological evaluation was performed using plain radiographs and computed tomography (CT) scans of the cervical spine. Assessments were done preoperatively, on the first postoperative day, and at 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months postoperatively. Cage subsidence was assessed by measuring the fused segment height (distance between the midpoints of the superior endplate of the upper vertebra and the inferior endplate of the lower vertebra). Subsidence was defined as a reduction of more than 3 mm in this height compared to immediate postoperative measurements. Segmental kyphosis was evaluated using the segmental Cobb angle (angle formed between the superior endplate of the upper vertebra and the inferior endplate of the lower vertebra of the operated segment). Data regarding demographics (age, gender), operative level, and serial radiological parameters were recorded on a pre-designed proforma.

All data were entered and analyzed using SPSS software version 22.0. Quantitative variables such as age, fused segment height, and segmental angles were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, median, and range. Qualitative variables (e.g., gender, subsidence rate, kyphosis rate) were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparison

between the two groups was performed using the independent samples t-test for continuous variables and the chi-square test for categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

This methodology ensured a standardized approach to patient selection, surgical technique, radiological assessment, and statistical analysis, allowing reliable comparison of the radiological outcomes between the two treatment modalities.

Results

A total of 40 patients with single-level cervical degenerative disc disease who underwent Anterior Cervical Discectomy and Fusion (ACDF) were included in this quasi-experimental study. Patients were equally divided into two groups: Group A (stand-alone PEEK cage, n=20) and Group B (PEEK cage with anterior plating, n=20). Both groups were comparable at baseline with respect to demographic and clinical characteristics.

Table 1: Comparison of Gender between Both Groups

Gender	Group A (Stand-alone PEEK Cage)		Group B (PEEK Cage with Plating)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	7	35.0%	8	40.0%
Female	13	65.0%	12	60.0%
Total	20	100.0%	20	100.0%

The majority of patients in both groups were female (65% in Group A and 60% in Group B). There was no statistically significant difference in gender distribution between the two groups ($p = 0.744$).

Table 2: Comparison of Age between Both Groups

Age Group	Group A		Group B	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
30–40 years	6	30.0%	8	40.0%
41–50 years	10	50.0%	7	35.0%
51–60 years	4	20.0%	5	25.0%
Mean \pm SD	44.70 \pm 8.151 years		42.40 \pm 9.196 years	

The mean age of patients in Group A was 44.70 ± 8.151 years, while in Group B it was 42.40 ± 9.196 years. The age distribution was comparable between both groups with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.850$).

Table 3: Comparison of Operative Level of ACDF between Both Groups

Level of ACDF	Group A		Group B		p-value
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	
C3–C4	3	15.0%	4	20.0%	0.929
C4–C5	4	20.0%	3	15.0%	
C5–C6	8	40.0%	9	45.0%	
C6–C7	5	25.0%	4	20.0%	
Total	20	100%	20	100%	

The most frequently operated level in both groups was C5–C6 (40% in Group A and 45% in Group B), followed by C6–C7. There was no significant difference in the distribution of operative levels between the two groups ($p = 0.929$).

Discussion

The present quasi-experimental study compared the radiological outcomes of cage subsidence and segmental kyphosis following single-level Anterior Cervical Discectomy and Fusion (ACDF) using stand-alone PEEK cages versus PEEK cages supplemented with anterior plating. The results demonstrated that the addition of anterior plating provided statistically superior radiological outcomes. Specifically, patients in Group B (PEEK cage with anterior plating) exhibited significantly less cage subsidence and better preservation of segmental lordosis compared to Group A (stand-alone PEEK cage) at 3-month and 6-month follow-ups. These findings are consistent with the biomechanical rationale and multiple previously published studies, reinforcing the mechanical advantages of supplemental plating in anterior cervical constructs.

Cage subsidence is a well-recognized phenomenon in ACDF, defined in this study as a reduction of more than 3 mm in fused segment height. In the current study, the overall subsidence rate was 25.0% in the stand-alone group versus 15.0% in the plated group ($p=0.009$). Progressive loss of disc height became statistically significant from the 3-month follow-up onward ($p=0.009$ at 3 months and $p=0.007$ at 6 months). This aligns closely with the findings of Song et al. (2009), who reported subsidence rates of 32.3% in cage-

alone cases compared to 9.7% in cage-with-plate constructs in single- and two-level ACDF. Similarly, Han et al. (2016) observed segmental subsidence in 36.1% of stand-alone cage patients versus only 15.6% in the plate-assisted group. Pinder and Sharp (2016) also documented significantly higher mean subsidence (1.68 mm vs 0.57 mm) and major subsidence rates (28% vs 7%) in the cage-alone cohort.

The higher subsidence observed in the stand-alone PEEK cage group can be explained by several biomechanical factors. Stand-alone cages rely primarily on the friction at the cage-endplate interface for initial stability. Micromotion at this interface, combined with axial compressive forces during the early phases of bone healing, leads to stress concentration and gradual settling of the cage into the vertebral endplates. In contrast, anterior plating converts the construct into a more rigid fixed-angle or semi-constrained system that effectively shares loads, resists compressive forces, and minimizes micromotion. This load-sharing effect helps preserve intervertebral height during the critical 6–12 week period when biological fusion is still maturing.

Regarding segmental kyphosis, the current study revealed a significantly higher rate in Group A (35.0%) compared to Group B (20.0%) ($p=0.028$). The mean segmental angle showed progressive loss of lordosis in the stand-alone group, with statistically significant differences at all follow-up intervals. These results corroborate the observations of Kast et al. (2009), who found a higher incidence of segmental kyphosis in certain cage designs, and Song et al. (2009), who reported kyphosis rates of 42.1% in the cage-alone group versus 10% in the plated group. Han et al. (2016) similarly noted kyphosis in 27.8% of stand-alone cases compared to 8.9% in plated cases. Kim et al. (2017) also demonstrated better maintenance of segmental alignment with plating, particularly in multi-level procedures, though benefits were still evident in single-level cases.

Loss of segmental lordosis is clinically important because even mild kyphotic deformity can lead to increased stress on adjacent segments, accelerated adjacent segment degeneration, and potential axial neck pain. By maintaining better sagittal alignment, anterior plating not only prevents local kyphosis but may also contribute to the long-term health of adjacent motion segments. The plated construct achieves this by providing immediate rigid fixation and counteracting the natural tendency of the cervical spine to collapse into kyphosis under gravitational and muscular forces after discectomy.

Several mechanisms explain the superiority of the cage-plus-plate construct. Anterior plates increase the stiffness of the segment in flexion, extension, and rotation, thereby reducing graft/cage pistoning. They also prevent anterior migration or extrusion of the cage. PEEK material, while

excellent for radiolucency and having an elastic modulus close to bone, still requires additional stabilization in the early postoperative period to optimize fusion biology and minimize subsidence. These findings are further supported by Chen et al. (2016), Mari et al. (2022), and Tang et al. (2023), who consistently reported better radiological parameters with plated constructs despite comparable short-term clinical outcomes in many series.

It is noteworthy that while radiological differences were clear and statistically significant in this study, clinical correlation was not assessed. Many authors have reported that radiological subsidence and mild kyphosis do not always translate into poorer patient-reported outcomes in the short term, especially in single-level disease. However, longer follow-up studies suggest that severe subsidence (>3–4 mm) and significant kyphosis are associated with higher rates of adjacent segment disease and revision surgery.

Conclusion

The current study demonstrates that supplementation of PEEK cages with anterior plating in single-level ACDF results in significantly lower rates of cage subsidence and segmental kyphosis compared to stand-alone PEEK cages. These superior radiological outcomes support the routine use of anterior plating, especially in younger patients, those with risk factors for subsidence (e.g., poor bone quality, larger cages, or endplate violation), or when optimal sagittal alignment is desired. Future large-scale, multicenter randomized controlled trials with extended follow-up and comprehensive clinical assessment are recommended to further validate these findings and establish definitive guidelines.

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References

1. Song KJ, Taghavi CE, Lee KB, Song JH, Eun JP. The efficacy of plate construct augmentation versus cage alone in anterior cervical fusion. *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*. 2009;34(26):2886-2892. doi:10.1097/BRS.0b013e3181b4f7c9
2. Han SY, Kim HW, Lee CY, Kim HR, Park DH. Stand-alone cages for anterior cervical fusion: Are there no problems? *Korean J Spine*. 2016;13(1):13-19. doi:10.14245/kjs.2016.13.1.13
3. Kim SY, Yoon SH, Kim D, Oh CH, Oh S. A prospective study with cage-only or cage-with-plate fixation in anterior cervical discectomy and interbody fusion of one and two levels. *J Korean Neurosurg Soc*. 2017;60(6):691-700. doi:10.3340/jkns.2017.0505.004

4. Kast E, Derakhshani S, Bothmann M, Oberle J. Subsidence after anterior cervical inter-body fusion. A randomized prospective clinical trial. *Neurosurg Rev.* 2009;32(2):207-214. doi:10.1007/s10143-008-0168-y
5. Pinder EM, Sharp DJ. Cage subsidence after anterior cervical discectomy and fusion using a cage alone or combined with anterior plate fixation. *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong).* 2016;24(1):97-100. doi:10.1177/230949901602400123
6. Chen Y, Lü G, Wang B, Li L, Kuang L. A comparison of anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) using self-locking stand-alone polyetheretherketone (PEEK) cage with ACDF using cage and plate in the treatment of three-level cervical degenerative spondylopathy: a retrospective study with 2-year follow-up. *Eur Spine J.* 2016;25(7):2255-2262. doi:10.1007/s00586-016-4557-6
7. Mari AR, Zeeshan QM, Uddin MM, et al. Comparison of radiological outcome in anterior cervical discectomy and fusion: cage-only v/s cage and plate fixation. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2022;16(5):1033-1035.
8. Tang L, Liu X, Lu Y, et al. Clinical and imaging outcomes of self-locking stand-alone cages and anterior cage-with-plate in three-level anterior cervical discectomy and fusion: a retrospective comparative study. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2023;18:276. doi:10.1186/s13018-023-03758-2
9. Song KJ, Taghavi CE, Lee KB, Song JH, Eun JP. The efficacy of plate construct augmentation versus cage alone in anterior cervical fusion. *Spine.* 2009;34(26):2886-2892.
10. Han SY, Kim HW, Lee CY, Kim HR, Park DH. Stand-alone cages for anterior cervical fusion: are there no problems? *Korean J Spine.* 2016;13(1):13-19.
11. Kim SY, Yoon SH, Kim D, Oh CH, Oh S. A prospective study with cage-only or cage-with-plate fixation in anterior cervical discectomy and interbody fusion of one and two levels. *J Korean Neurosurg Soc.* 2017;60(6):691-700.
12. Kast E, Derakhshani S, Bothmann M, Oberle J. Subsidence after anterior cervical inter-body fusion. A randomized prospective clinical trial. *Neurosurg Rev.* 2009;32(2):207-214.
13. Pinder EM, Sharp DJ. Cage subsidence after anterior cervical discectomy and fusion using a cage alone or combined with anterior plate fixation. *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong).* 2016;24(1):97-100.
14. Chen Y, Lü G, Wang B, Li L, Kuang L. A comparison of anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF) using self-locking stand-alone polyetheretherketone (PEEK) cage with ACDF using cage and plate... *Eur Spine J.* 2016;25(7):2255-2262.
15. Mari AR, et al. Comparison of radiological outcome in anterior cervical discectomy and fusion: cage-only v/s cage and plate fixation. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2022;16(5):1033-1035.
16. Tang L, et al. Clinical and imaging outcomes of self-locking stand-alone cages and anterior cage-with-plate in three-level anterior cervical discectomy and fusion. *J Orthop Surg Res.* 2023;18:276.

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